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CROSS-CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT “GRATITUDE”

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Gratitude is a feeling of appreciation felt by the recipient of kindness, gifts, help, favors, or other types of generosity, to the giver of aforesaid gifts. The experience of gratitude has historically been a focus of several world religions. Besides, it aroused the curiosity of ancient, medieval and modern philosophers, and continues to engross contemporary philosophers as well. This concept tends to be a positive aptitude of a person for any help received in a particular situation. When comparing *gratitude* with the word *indebtedness*, we find that gratitude can motivate the recipient of aid to seek out their benefactor and to improve their relationship with them whereas the latter emotion can prove the otherwise i.e. a person being under obligation to make some repayment tries to avoid those who helped them.

Moreover, it would also be better to define what a concept is. Although dictionary definitions of a ‘concept’ may vary, there is some consensus for it being ‘an abstract idea generalized from particular instances’ which seems not enough to construct a firm definition. Hence, Spitzer (1975) unifying some authors’ concept interpretations claims that it is the “general processes of cognition”.

The aim of this study is to investigate the components of the literary concept – *Gratitude* i.e. notional, image-bearing and evaluative components. The images coined in this concept are represented via constructing various conceptual schemes, which characterizes good social feelings of humanity.

1. Notional component of the concept “Gratitude”

The word originates from the Latin word *gratus* which means “pleasing, thankful”. Several online dictionaries such as Collins Online Dictionary, Merriam-Webster Dictionary and Cambridge Dictionary provide a universally identical meaning of this lexical unit. We can note that the word *gratitude* comes in the form of a noun, but does not have a verb form.

NOUN:

Collins Online Dictionary:

Gratitude is the state of feeling grateful.

Merriam-Webster Dictionary:

a feeling of appreciation or thanks

Cambridge Dictionary:

the feeling or quality of being grateful

Similarly, in the Russian language, the word “Благодарность” cannot be a verb, and it functions as a noun only. The Russian dictionary compiled by S. I. Ozhegov defines it as:

1. Чувство признательности к кому-н. за оказанное добро, внимание, услугу. *Принять с благодарностью что-н. Принести б. кому-н. Сделать что-н. в знак благодарности или в б. за что-н.*

2. *только мн.* Слова, выражающие эти чувства (разг.). *Рассыпаться в благодарностях.*

3. Официальное выражение высокой оценки чьего-н. труда, действий. *Объявить б. в приказе. Получить б. от дирекции.*

A phraseological unit can be defined as a non-motivated word-group that cannot be freely made up in speech, but is reproduced as a ready-made unit. It is a group of words whose meaning cannot be deduced by examining the meaning of the constituent lexemes. In other words, according to Prof. Kunin A.V., phraseological units are stable word-groups with partially or fully transferred meanings (Babich, 2010). The phrases associated with this word are not many. Some phraseological units are as follows:

Phrase: **Owe a debt of gratitude to**

Meaning: to have a good reason to be very grateful to (someone)

Example: The whole town owes a debt of gratitude to the people who organized the parade.

Phrase: **a token of your appreciation/gratitude/thanks**

Meaning: something that you do for someone or that you give them as a way of showing your feelings towards them

Example: He brought her some flowers as a token of his gratitude.

1. Image-bearing component of the concept “Gratitude”

The image-bearing component encompasses the information of connotative and associative plane (Tarasova, 2010). Throughout the literary materials on the internet the following example sentences that show the created images of the concept under analysis have been found.

Gratitude for kindness is a marked **trait** in the Indian character, and Pulin bethought him of the old fable of the Lion and Mouse.

Examples of error: “*Gratitude* is a forcible and active **principle** in good and generous minds.”

Gratitude was the absorbing **emotion**.

Gratitude had been the **foundation** of their own now many-year-long friendship.

I told him with freedom, I feared mostly their treachery and ill usage of me, if I put my life in their hands; for that *gratitude* was no inherent **virtue** in the nature of man, nor did men always square their dealings by the obligations they had received, so much as they did by the advantages they expected.

The *gratitude* of the family was a **matter** of little consequence to me.

Gratitude is indeed a **duty** which we are bound to pay, but which benefactors cannot exact.

If *gratitude* be the proper **description** of that sentiment which one feels towards the unconscious bestower of an unintended benefit, I acknowledge myself sincerely grateful to the honourable gentleman (Mr. Macdonald) who has introduced the present motion.

Thus, should anyone say that parsimony is frugality, that *gratitude* is **justice**, that this or that action is or is not temperate: however specious these and the like propositions may at first sight seem, yet when we come to press them, and examine nicely what they contain, we shall find that it all amounts to nothing but the signification of those terms.

Is *gratitude* a **possession** of man only, or do the lower orders know it also?

Sir, *gratitude* is a **fruit** of great cultivation; you do not find it among gross people.

That your course may seem more reasonable, and appear to be the outcome of your own inclination, you will on such occasions be able to say that you are under obligation to him for his readiness and gallantry--always use these words--when your daughter was in the brimming river; but that your *gratitude* can be only a **memory**, since he has leagued himself against a cause so near to the heart, and so supremely in the interest, of every man and woman and child in the colony of Red River.

Gratitude's a heavy **burden** to a proud Soul. - Nobody loves this Oswald -- Yourself, you do not love him.

Thus, the concept *Gratitude* is represented mostly as a positive image like a trait, a principle, an emotion, a foundation, a virtue, a matter, a duty, a description, justice, a possession, a fruit, a memory, and a burden. In one case only can it be seen to have a negative connotation.

Figure 1. An image-bearing component of the *Gratitude* concept

1. Evaluative component of the concept “Gratitude”

The evaluative component can be analyzed on the basis of the word’s effect, role and benefits for people and society.

Gratitude may also serve to reinforce future prosocial behavior in benefactors. When people are grateful, they don’t forget or refuse the negative part of life; they just see the good things about it. People who are more grateful than others are more likely to overcome hardships. Emmons, McCullough, and Tsang found that gratitude comes from personality traits such as high positive emotions, openness, and happiness. Recent research has also found that these traits can be acquired by expressing gratitude. Benefits of expressing gratitude are greater happiness, higher self-esteem, empathy, and stronger relationships. When faced with negativity, resilience is shown as more positive emotions are recognized than negative ones. It can be implied that gratitude causes an increase motivation to make connections and seek positive meanings of life events. Individuals who practice expressing gratitude also improved overall health by increasing physical activity, improved sleep, fewer health care visits, and better nutrition.

According to McCullough et al, the link between spirituality and gratitude has recently become a popular subject of study. While these two characteristics are certainly not dependent on each other, studies have found that spirituality is capable of enhancing a person’s ability to be grateful and therefore, those who regularly attend religious services or participate in religious activities are more

likely to have a greater sense of gratitude in all areas of life. Thus, in most major religious traditions there is a tendency amongst people to favor gratitude as a gift from God. Apart from that, worship with gratitude to God is a regular matter in such religions and therefore, the concept of gratitude pervades religious texts, teachings, and traditions. For this reason, it is one of the most common emotions that religions aim to provoke and maintain in followers and is regarded as a universal religious sentiment.

1. Conclusion

To conclude, the analysis of the representation of *Gratitude* concept in language and literature reiterates the fact that it has a highly positive connotation used in the form of metaphors. Therefore, it can really help nurture people for only goodness being closely related to the world's major religions.

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ТОВУШ ОРТТИРИЛИШИ ВА ТУШИШИ (Наманган қипчоқ шевалари мисолида)

Ҳ.Маматисмоилова, НамДУ тадқиқотчиси

Товушларнинг орттирилиши ва тушиши, сўз шаклларида торайиб, кенгайиши фақат ҳозирги замон туркий тиллардагина бўлмай, қадимги ёзма ёдгорликларда ҳам қайд қилинган. Маҳмуд Қошғарий бундай ҳодисаларни турклар *чумчуқ*, *тамгақ* деб талаффуз қилсалар, қипчоқлар *чумуқ*, *тамақ* деб талаффуз этадилар, уни талаффузда осонлик бўлсин учун шундай дейдилар, деб изоҳлайди¹⁸⁶. Ҳозирги ўзбек шевалари – ҳудудий сўзлашув жарёнларида,

¹ Қошғарий М. Девону луғотит турк. I. – Тошкент, 1960. – Б.69.